

KINDERGARTEN TEACHERS' CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT STYLES AND LEARNERS' LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT IN THE DIVISION OF LUCENA CITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11630132>

ABSTRACT

This study intends to determine the classroom management styles of kindergarten teachers in the Division of Lucena City and the level of engagement of kindergarten learners across behavioral, emotional, and cognitive aspects. It utilized descriptive-correlational research design. The data were statistically analyzed using percentage formula and mean score. Moreover, the significant relationship between kindergarten teachers' classroom management style and learners' level of engagement was statistically analyzed using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r). The study involved 120 public school kindergarten teachers distributed across its districts: North District (34 teachers), East District (22 teachers), West District (30 teachers), and South District (34 teachers). The findings revealed that the interactionist style was the most practiced classroom management style among public school kindergarten teachers in the Division of Lucena City. Meanwhile, learners' level of engagement across behavioral, emotional, and cognitive dimensions during the first and second quarters of School Year 2023-2024 were on the developing level (sometimes engaged). It was also found that there was a significant correlation (weak positive correlation) between interactionist classroom management style and learners' emotional engagement during the second quarter. Thus, a lesson plan model utilizing interactionist classroom management style highlighting emotional development among kindergarten learners was proposed by the researcher.

Keywords: *Behavioral Engagement, Classroom Management Style, Cognitive Engagement, Emotional Engagement, Interactionist, Interventionist, Level of Engagement, Non-Interventionist*

INTRODUCTION

Classroom management is a crucial aspect of teaching as it encompasses various elements, such as time management, behavior management, and fostering positive relationships with the learners. A safe and stimulating learning environment is essential to ensure learners are engaged in learning activities and are motivated to achieve their academic goals. Furthermore, classroom management can be viewed as a complex concept that involves a teacher's personality, professional behavior, and competencies needed to perform their roles successfully.

Martin and Baldwin's theoretical model offers a comprehensive understanding of classroom management with three broad dimensions: Personality, Teaching, and Discipline. The Personality dimension pertains to a teacher's actions contributing to learners' personal growth and emotional well-being. The Teaching dimension relates to a teacher's actions that establish and maintain learners' learning activities. In contrast, the Discipline dimension concerns a teacher's strategies and actions to maintain appropriate standards of behavior in the classroom. Based on Wolfgang and Glickman's explanation of the relationship between teachers' behavior patterns and their beliefs about learners' personalities and motivations, the Martin and Baldwin model identifies three classroom management styles: Interventionist, Non-Interventionist, and Interactionist. Each style reflects a teacher's beliefs about how much control they should have over the classroom environment. To assess their classroom management style, teachers can use a self-assessment instrument based on the Martin and Baldwin model. Although each teacher may use all three styles, one typically dominates their behavior in the classroom. By understanding their dominant style, teachers can reflect on their strengths and areas for improvement and adopt more effective classroom management strategies to enhance learners' engagement and learning.

Kindergarten learners' emotional, cognitive, and behavioral engagement refers to the level of participation and involvement of young children in the learning process, including their feelings, thoughts, and actions related to the learning activities. Emotional engagement involves the affective aspect of learning, such as the level of interest, motivation, and enjoyment that learners experience during classroom activities. Cognitive engagement refers to the degree to which learners actively participate in the learning process, such as their level of attention, comprehension, and problem-solving skills. Finally, behavioral engagement relates to learners' observable behaviors in the classroom, such as their attendance, participation, and cooperation with teachers and peers. Together, these three types of engagement play a crucial role in kindergarten learners' academic and social development, as they impact the quality and depth of learning experiences and ultimately shape their future success in school and beyond.

Moreover, the kindergarten years, typically between the ages of 4 and 6, are considered a critical period in a child's development. During this time, children undergo significant

cognitive, social, emotional, and physical growth. They are particularly receptive to learning and develop fundamental skills and abilities that will serve as building blocks for future learning and development. The quality of learning experiences during kindergarten can have lasting effects on a child's future academic and personal success. Research suggests that early educational experiences strongly influence various outcomes, such as academic achievement, cognitive abilities, social skills, and emotional well-being. A strong foundation established during kindergarten can contribute to a positive trajectory in later school years and overall life outcomes. Kindergarten sets the stage for subsequent academic progress. Children acquire essential skills like literacy, numeracy, problem-solving, and critical thinking during this period. A high-quality kindergarten experience with practical instruction and engaging learning activities can foster a love for learning, curiosity, and a solid academic foundation that supports later educational achievements. Beyond academic outcomes, the kindergarten years also play a vital role in shaping a child's personal development. Kindergarten provides opportunities for socialization, emotional growth, and the development of social skills such as cooperation, empathy, and communication. Positive experiences during this time can enhance self-esteem, self-confidence, and overall social-emotional well-being, contributing to success in personal relationships and overall life satisfaction.

This study explores the relationship between classroom management styles of kindergarten teachers and the emotional, cognitive, and behavioral engagement of their learners in the Division of Lucena City. The kindergarten years are a critical period for children's development, and the quality of their learning experiences can have a significant impact on their future academic and personal success. Therefore, it is essential to investigate the classroom management styles that are most effective in promoting engagement among young learners. Thus, this study aims to contribute to the existing literature on classroom management and enhance the understanding of how teacher behavior and classroom management practices affect learner engagement. The findings of this study may have significant implications for improving teaching and learning practices in kindergarten classrooms in the Division of Lucena City and beyond.

Research Questions

1. What extent of a particular classroom management style is practiced by kindergarten teachers among:
 - 1.1 interventionist style;
 - 1.2 interactionist style; and
 - 1.3 non-interventionist style?
2. What is the level of engagement of kindergarten learners in terms of:
 - 2.1 behavioral engagement;
 - 2.2 emotional engagement; and
 - 2.3 cognitive engagement:
 - 2.3.1 *literacy*; and
 - 2.3.2 *numeracy*?

3. Is there a significant relationship between classroom management styles practiced by kindergarten teachers and the level of engagement of kindergarten learners during:
 - 3.1 first quarter; and
 - 3.2 second quarter?
 4. What lesson plan model can be proposed by the researcher from the findings of the study?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the correlation between teachers' classroom management styles and learners' level of engagement. The study utilized a descriptive research design to assess teachers' preferences by adapting a questionnaire for coding purposes. Similarly, the research design was descriptive to assess learners' engagement levels. Furthermore, the study is descriptive-correlational, aiming to determine relationship between different variables.

Research Locale

The researcher conducted her study in the Division of Lucena City. Lucena City is composed of four districts with 45 public elementary schools respectively (North District: 14 schools, East District: 10 schools, West District: 11 schools, and South District: 10 schools).

Research Population and Sample

The researcher employed a total enumeration sampling technique, encompassing all 120 public school kindergarten teachers within the Division of Lucena City. The division comprises 120 public school kindergarten teachers distributed across its districts: North District (34 teachers), East District (22 teachers), West District (30 teachers), and South District (34 teachers).

Table 1

Public School Kindergarten Teachers in the Division of Lucena City

District	No. of Kindergarten Teachers
North	34
East	22
West	30
South	34

Total	120
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Research Instrument

The researcher utilized adapted questionnaire in collecting data in kindergarten teachers' classroom management styles. This was interpreted as follows:

Table 2

Classroom Management Style Scale and Qualitative Description

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	4.50- 5.00	Very Great Extent	It signifies a high frequency and consistency in implementing these practices.
4	3.50- 4.49	Great Extent	It signifies regular implementation with considerable effectiveness, though it may lack the consistency of the highest level.
3	2.50- 3.49	Moderately Extent	It signifies a moderate frequency of practice implementation, reflecting an average level of effectiveness.
2	1.50- 2.49	Low Extent	It signifies an infrequent application of practices indicating a lack of regular engagement.
1	1.00- 1.49	Very Low Extent	It signifies a complete absence of the specified practices in daily operations.

The researcher then gathered the learners' level of engagement through kindergarten quarterly assessment result during first and second quarters. This was interpreted as follows:

Table 3

Level of Engagement Qualitative Description

Level	Indicators
(B) Beginning	The learner rarely demonstrates the competency. The learner rarely participates in class activities and/or initiates independent works.

	The learner shows interest in doing tasks but needs close supervision.
(D) Developing	The learner sometimes demonstrates the competency. The learner sometimes participates, with minimal supervision. The learner progresses continuously in doing assigned tasks.
(C) Consistent	The learner always demonstrates the competency. The learner always participates in different activities, works independently. The learner always performs tasks, and is advanced in some aspects.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher initiated the data collection process by seeking permission from the author of the adapted questionnaire via email. Subsequently, the researcher obtained approval from relevant authorities to gather data in the chosen locale. Once the schedule was confirmed, the researcher prepared her instruments, including an endorsement letter and necessary materials for the study. The researcher then commenced data gathering by administering the adapted questionnaire to the kindergarten teachers.

Upon completion of data collection, the researcher proceeded to interpret the gathered information from the questionnaire to analyze the teachers' preferred classroom management styles. Additionally, the researcher obtained data on kindergarten learners' level of engagement from recorded quarterly assessments during the first and second quarters. Subsequently, the researcher interpreted the data to analyze the level of engagement among the kindergarten learners.

Statistical Treatment of Data

For **Part I** of the study, which focused on classroom management styles, the statistical treatment involved using the Weighted Mean Formula to calculate the average preference for each management style among the kindergarten teachers. This formula considers the varying importance or weight assigned to each response option in the questionnaire.

For **Part II**, which examined the level of engagement among kindergarten learners, the statistical treatment involved utilizing the percentage formula to determine the proportion of learners actively engaged in classroom activities. This formula calculates the percentage of engaged learners based on the total number of learners assessed during the first and second quarters.

To test the hypothesis regarding the relationship between classroom management style and learners' level of engagement, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed. This statistical measure assesses the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables, in this case, styles of classroom management and the level of learners' engagement.

Scope and Delimitation

This study probed only into identifying the extent of practice of classroom management styles of kindergarten teachers and the level of engagement of learners.

The responses of kindergarten teachers served as the basis for lesson plan model.

This study is limited to 120 public school kindergarten teachers in the Division of Lucena City.

The modified and adapted survey questionnaire served as the primary instrument in collecting the data needed in the study in terms of teachers' classroom management style while the data for the learners' level of engagement were gathered from the kindergarten quarterly assessment result during first and second quarters of School Year 2023-2024.

RESULTS

Part I. Extent of a Particular Classroom Management Style Practiced by Kindergarten Teachers

Table 4

Extent of Practice of Interventionist Classroom Management Style Among Kindergarten Teachers

<i>Interventionist</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. When, during the class, one of my learners' loud laughs or starts crying, I get angry because he/she disturbs the class and I scold him/her.	2.53	Moderately Extent
2. I use to reward each learner achievement with good grade and to assess every failure with a bad grade or at least I criticize it.	3.97	Great Extent
3. I try to activate learners in class by calling them on.	4.76	Very Great Extent
4. I get angry when a learner disturbs class or harasses other learners, I immediately demand him/her to stop such behavior, or I'll have to punish him/her.	2.94	Moderately Extent
5. If any of the learners does not work during the class, I announce that he/she will stay during the break to complete the task, give him/her more extensive homework or give him/her a bad mark.	3.32	Moderately Extent
6. When I notice inappropriate, rude behavior, I always reprimand learners for that.	3.39	Moderately Extent
7. I believe that during the classes, learners have to keep quiet and listen to me in order to learn something.	4.13	Great Extent
8. When learners are restless during the class, I interrupt class explicitly requiring them to behave normally.	3.59	Great Extent
9. In order to ensure that learners will work sitting at their desks, I have to control them and exhort to work.	3.48	Moderately Extent

10. I require learners to do exactly what I tell them because I know that this is the only way they could learn the material.	3.53	Great Extent
	3.56	Great Extent

Source: Djigic, G. (2014). *Inventory for Teachers Self-Assessment in Classroom Management Styles - Development and its Psychometric Characteristics*

Legend:

4.50-5.00 *Very Great Extent*

3.50-4.49 *Great Extent*

2.50-3.49 *Moderately Extent*

1.50-2.49 *Low Extent*

1.00-1.49 *Very Low Extent*

Table 4 illustrates the interventionist classroom management style as practiced by kindergarten teachers, with a weighted mean of **3.56**, indicating a Great Extent response overall. Among the interventionist style practices, item 3, which states, "I try to activate learners in a class by calling them on," has the highest weighted mean of **4.76**, indicating a Very Great Extent response. Basically, learners at young age have short attention spans and easily gets distracted, thus, this suggests that kindergarten teachers actively employ strategies to engage learners such as by calling on them during class activities. Learners however, who participate in class are therefore be most likely more focused, better learners, and higher thinkers. An interventionist classroom management comprises of actions taken by teachers to create a supportive environment for the cognitive, behavioral, social and emotional development of learners (Korpershoek, 2016). A teacher who cares about his/her learners transmits knowledge effectively and has a good interaction with them due to the creation of an emotional link and environment (Kabeera, 2019).

Moreover, using rewards (item 2), getting learners' attention (item 7), establishing classroom rules (item 8), and directing kindergarten learners (item 10), are practiced to a Great Extent by kindergarten teachers. Interventionist classroom management involves five types of actions to help a teacher to offer high quality classroom management; (a) teachers must be caring to learners, (b) develop supportive relationship with learners, (c) organize and implement instructions in ways that optimize learners' access to learning, (d) teachers encouraging learners' engagement in academic tasks, and (e) using of group management methods (Korpershoek, 2016).

Table 5*Extent of Practice of Interactionist Classroom Management Style Among Kindergarten Teachers*

<i>Interactionist</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I believe that learners learn best when I allow them to freely express opinions, ideas, and suggestions.	4.68	Very Great Extent
2. I seek to use various types of teaching activities to encourage active participation of all my learners during the lesson.	4.65	Very Great Extent
3. While learners work on their place, I stand in the place from which I have a view of the whole classroom and access to the learners who seek help.	4.76	Very Great Extent
4. I believe that learners should know that their success is my success as well and that they have the right to make a mistake, because they can correct it with my help.	4.3	Great Extent
5. I believe that it is important for learners to understand why it is important for them personally what they are learning; they can be free to choose the way in which they would like to learn.	4.42	Great Extent
6. It is important to me how do my learners feel and what they need.	4.83	Very Great Extent
7. If a learner disturbs class or other learners, I remind him/her on rules of behavior that all of us in the class are trying to respect.	4.57	Very Great Extent
8. When one of the learners does not work during the class, I approach him/her, checking what is going on and I am trying to animate his/her activity providing him/her the needed assistance.	4.63	Very Great Extent
9. Appropriate working atmosphere is important to me, so when I perceive an undiscipline learner, I want to solve the problem together with him/her in order to proceed with further work.	4.49	Great Extent
10. In order to maintain discipline in class, I use to remind learners on rules adapted by their own participation.	4.48	Great Extent
	4.58	Very Great Extent

Source: Djigic, G. (2014). *Inventory for Teachers Self-Assessment in Classroom Management Styles - Development and its Psychometric Characteristics*

Legend:

4.50-5.00 *Very Great Extent*

3.50-4.49 *Great Extent*

2.50-3.49 *Moderately Extent*

1.50-2.49 *Low Extent*

1.00-1.49 *Very Low Extent*

Table 5 presents the interactionist classroom management style as practiced by kindergarten teachers to a Very Great Extent with a weighted mean of **4.58**. The table shows that item 6, "It is important to me how my learners feel and what they need" has the highest weighted mean of **4.83**, and is practiced to a Very Great Extent by kindergarten teachers, followed by item 3, "While learners work on their place, I stand in the place from which I have a view of the whole classroom and access to the learners who seek help" to a Very Great Extent with a weighted mean of **4.76**, and item 1, "I believe that learners learn best when I allow them to express opinions, ideas, and suggestions freely" to a Very Great Extent with a weighted mean of **4.68**.

It can be viewed that kindergarten teachers in the Division of Lucena City utilized the interactionist style as classroom management to merely a Very Great Extent and Great

Extent. Teachers who practice the interactionist style encourage interaction and cooperation in the classroom, respect learner’s personalities, and appreciate the initiatives, interests, and needs of learners (Ghazi, 2017). Hence, teachers share the responsibility inside the classroom with learners.

Table 6
Extent of Practice of Non-Interventionist Classroom Management Style Among Kindergarten Teachers

<i>Non-Interventionist</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. While learners are working sitting at their desks, I do something else.	3.53	Great Extent
2. My reference to the rules of behavior in class could not greatly contribute to the regulation of learners’ behavior.	3.28	Moderately Extent
3. When I assign the task to learners for work in the classroom, I think it is best for them to deal with it themselves without any help or control.	3.9	Great Extent
4. My duty is to assess learners, not to explain them my views regarding their efforts.	2.68	Moderately Extent
5. It is not up to me to bring up my learners during the classes.	2.56	Moderately Extent
6. My attention during the class is focused on teaching the appropriate unit, and it is only up to the learners whether or not they will participate in the work group.	3.03	Moderately Extent
7. I do not react to inappropriate behavior of some learners, but occasionally point out that each learner is responsible for his/her own behavior and learning.	3.54	Great Extent
8. I think that the learners themselves should assess whether and how the learning content is important to them personally.	3.63	Great Extent
9. It’s not my job to deal with the feelings and needs of the learners.	1.48	Very Low Extent
10. While teaching a lesson, I do not deal with the reactions of learners.	1.6	Low Extent
	2.92	Moderately Extent

Source: Djigic, G. (2014). *Inventory for Teachers Self-Assessment in Classroom Management Styles - Development and its Psychometric Characteristics*

Legend:

- 4.50-5.00 *Very Great Extent*
- 3.50-4.49 *Great Extent*
- 2.50-3.49 *Moderately Extent*
- 1.50-2.49 *Low Extent*
- 1.00-1.49 *Very Low Extent*

Table 6 presents the non-interventionist classroom management style as practiced by kindergarten teachers with a weighted mean of **2.92** and verbally interpreted as Moderately Extent. Hence, non-interventionist style is moderately utilized by public school kindergarten teachers in Lucena City. As it could be gleaned from the table, item 9, stating that “It is not my job to deal with the feelings and needs of the learners” has the lowest weighted mean of **1.48** indicating a Very Low Extent, thus, kindergarten teachers in Lucena City really takes into consideration learners’ feelings and needs in classroom

settings. The non-interventionist approach is based on the belief that a person has his own needs that tend to express and accomplish them, so the teacher has minimal control. On the other hand, teaching in kindergarten requires teachers an “extending hand” for learners. Although, they agree with item 3 to a Great Extent, “When I assign the task to learners for work in the classroom, I think it is best for them to deal with it themselves without any help or control”, with a weighted mean of **3.9**. It is also vital that as learners progress, minimal supervision or working independently may be implemented. Meanwhile, item 10, stating “While teaching a lesson, I do not deal with the reactions of learners”, has a low weighted mean of **1.6** indicating a Low Extent. Kindergarten teachers disagree with this practice, as learners’ reactions when teaching are an indication of how they are engaged in classroom teaching.

The non-interventionist classroom management style which is more constructive than the interfering strategy, should lead to constructive behavior and the growth of self-discipline, thus, the learners’ moral behavior can be high (Ghazi, 2017).

Table 7

Summary of Results of Extent of Practice of Classroom Management Styles Among Kindergarten Teachers

Classroom Management Styles	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Interventionist	3.56	Great Extent	2
Interactionist	4.58	Very Great Extent	1
Non-Interventionist	2.92	Moderately Extent	3

Legend:

4.50-5.00 *Very Great Extent*

3.50-4.49 *Great Extent*

2.50-3.49 *Moderately Extent*

1.50-2.49 *Low Extent*

1.00-1.49 *Very Low Extent*

Table 7 reveals the ranking of classroom management styles as practiced by kindergarten teachers in the Division of Lucena City. It shows that kindergarten teachers integrate interactionist style in teaching to a Very Great Extent with a weighted mean of **4.58**, followed by interventionist style to a Great Extent with a weighted mean of **3.56**, and non-interventionist to a Moderately Extent with a weighted mean of **2.92**. Although each teacher may use all these three styles, one typically dominates their behavior in the classroom. By understanding their dominant style, teachers can reflect on their strengths and areas for improvement and adapt more effective classroom management strategies to enhance learners' engagement and learning. The results shows that interactionist style is dominant in kindergarten teachers as compared to interventionist and non-interventionist styles.

In addition, Kaur (2020) revealed that teachers who used an interactionist classroom management style had the highest level of learner engagement compared to teachers who used interventionist and non-interventionist styles.

Likewise, on a study by Sulistiyani (2018) on the correlation between classroom management styles and learner engagement in kindergarten. The results revealed that teachers who used an interactionist classroom management style had the highest level of learner engagement compared to teachers who used interventionist and non-interventionist styles.

Part II. Level of Engagement of Kindergarten Learners

Table 8
Kindergarten Learners' Level of Behavioral Engagement

Quarter (SY 2023-2024)	Number of Learners	<i>Health, Well Being, and Motor Development</i>					
		(C) Consistent		(D) Developing		(B) Beginning	
1st	5494	373	6.79 %	3637	66.20 %	1484	27.01 %
2nd	5440	1201	22.08 %	3465	63.69 %	774	14.23 %

Legend:

C-Consistent (*The learner always demonstrates the competency.*)

D-Developing (*The learner sometimes demonstrates the competency.*)

B-Beginning (*The learner rarely demonstrates the competency.*)

Table 8 reveals the result of kindergarten learners' level of behavioral engagement in terms of health, well-being, and motor development. During the first quarter, majority of the learners, or **66.20 %** (3637 learners), belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), while **27.01 %** (1484 learners), belongs to the beginning level (rarely engaged). Meanwhile, the remaining **6.79 %** (373 learners), belongs to the consistent level (always engaged).

Kindergarten learners' behavioral engagement during the first quarter falls under the developing level. Behavioral development in kindergarten describes how learners actively participate, comply with the rules and expectations of the classroom, and exhibit positive behaviors in the learning environment. As shown in the result, during the beginning quarter, these traits are not yet observed and most kindergarten learners belong to the developing and beginning level. Meanwhile, during the second quarter majority of the learners, or **63.69 %** (3465 learners), belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), while **22.08 %** (1201 learners), belongs to the consistent level (always engaged), meanwhile the remaining **14.23%** (774 learners), belongs to the beginning level (rarely engaged). Most of the learners still falls under the developing level during the second quarter, yet an increase in the consistent level was revealed. Learners become

more familiar with the classroom setting. Recognition, familiarization, and exposure to extended periods in an environment display higher levels of behavioral engagement.

Teachers' role is very important in the development of learners' behavior. Learners spend a majority of their time within the educational institution, where they not only acquire academic knowledge but also keenly observe and learn from their teachers. When learners believe that their teacher genuinely cares about their success and evaluates both their strengths and weaknesses, they are more driven to succeed in both school and in life in general. When learners receive constructive criticism and help to strengthen their areas of weakness, it is easier to maintain their motivation.

Furthermore, Chang and Chen (2019) discovered that kindergarten learners in classrooms with authoritative teachers demonstrated higher levels of behavioral engagement and academic achievement, while learners in classrooms with authoritarian or permissive management styles showed lower levels of engagement and achievement.

Table 9
Kindergarten Learners' Level of Emotional Engagement

Quarter (SY 2023-2024)	Number of Learners	Socio-Emotional Development					
		(C) Consistent		(D) Developing		(B) Beginning	
1st	5494	485	8.83 %	3561	64.82 %	1448	26.36 %
2nd	5440	1131	20.79 %	3482	64.01 %	827	15.20 %

Legend:

C-Consistent (*The learner always demonstrates the competency.*)

D-Developing (*The learner sometimes demonstrates the competency.*)

B-Beginning (*The learner rarely demonstrates the competency.*)

Table 9 shows the result of kindergarten learners' level of emotional engagement. During the first quarter, majority of the learners, or **64.82 %** (3561 learners), belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), while **26.36 %** (1448 learners), belongs to the beginning level (rarely engaged). Meanwhile, the remaining **8.83 %** (485 learners) belongs to the consistent level (always engaged). Emotional engagement of kindergarten learners falls under the developing level during the first quarter. Transitioning from a home environment to a school classroom can create a variety of emotional challenges for young children. Thus, teachers and learners must have supportive and nurturing interactions. A sense of trust and emotional connection is fostered by teachers who demonstrate empathy, understanding, and responsiveness to the emotional needs of the learners, which in turn encourages learning engagement. Learners tend to be more emotionally engaged in kindergarten settings that offer a healthy emotional climate that is defined by warmth, acceptance, and support. Learners are more likely to actively participate in learning when they feel secure, appreciated, and supported emotionally. Moreover, during the second quarter majority of the learners or **64.01 %** (3637 learners), belongs to

the developing level (sometimes engaged), while **20.79 %** (1131 learners), belongs to the consistent level (always engaged). Meanwhile the remaining **15.20%** (827 learners), belongs to the beginning level (rarely engaged). An increase of consistent learners was revealed during the second quarter. Emotional engagement in kindergarten is influenced by play-based activities and interactions with classmates. Learners can explore their emotions through play, learn social skills, and form emotional ties with others. Emotional involvement and social-emotional development are enhanced by cooperative play and favorable peer interactions. Emotional engagement in kindergarten is often facilitated when learning experiences are personally relevant and exciting to learners. When activities align with their interests, experiences, and developmental needs, learners are more likely to be emotionally engaged and motivated to participate.

Emotional engagement in kindergarten is often facilitated when learning experiences are personally relevant and exciting to learners. When activities align with their interests, experiences, and developmental needs, learners are more likely to be emotionally engaged and motivated to participate. Similarly, learners have the chance to express and control their emotions in kindergarten. Learners’ emotional engagement can be increased by teachers who foster an environment that is welcoming and supportive of emotional expression while simultaneously teaching techniques for emotional control.

Thompson and Smith (2016) also found that kindergarten learners in classrooms with authoritative teachers demonstrated higher levels of academic achievement and positive social development compared to those in classrooms with authoritarian or permissive management styles.

Moreover, in the study by Farran (2015), findings indicate that both instructional support and emotional support, when combined, were significant predictors of the intensity of children's learning engagement. Moreover, the impact of instructional practices on learning engagement was contingent upon the emotional atmosphere within the classroom. Specifically, instructional practices had a more significant effect on the overall level of engagement in classrooms characterized by a more positive emotional tone. The study suggests that a supportive emotional environment enhances the effectiveness of instructional practices in promoting learner engagement. Therefore, fostering instructional and emotional support is essential for creating an optimal learning environment that maximizes learner engagement and learning outcomes.

Table 10
Kindergarten Learners’ Level of Cognitive Engagement-Literacy

Quarter (SY 2023-2024)	Number of Learners	Literacy					
		(C) Consistent		(D) Developing		(B) Beginning	
1st	5494	367	6.68 %	2612	47.54 %	2515	45.78 %
2nd	5440	948	17.43 %	2954	54.30 %	1538	28.27 %

Legend:

C-Consistent (*The learner always demonstrates the competency.*)

D-Developing (*The learner sometimes demonstrates the competency.*)

B-Beginning (*The learner rarely demonstrates the competency.*)

Table 10 presents the result of kindergarten learners' level of cognitive engagement in literacy. During the first quarter, majority of the learners, or **47.54 %** (2612 learners), belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), while **45.78 %** (2515 learners), belongs to the beginning level (rarely engaged), meanwhile the remaining **6.68 %** (367 learners), belongs to the consistent level (always engaged). A high number of learners falls under the developing and beginning level was revealed during the first quarter. Initially, kindergarten is the start of formal schooling, thus learners arrive to school mostly illiterate. Cognitive engagement is more likely to be cultivated in kindergarten programs that use inquiry-based methods, where kids are encouraged to explore, investigate, and ask questions. Higher-order thinking, problem-solving abilities, and curiosity are all encouraged by inquiry-based learning. Meanwhile, during the second quarter majority of the learners, or **54.30 %** (2954 learners), belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), while **28.27 %** (1538 learners), belongs to the beginning level (rarely engaged), meanwhile the remaining **17.43%** (948 learners), belongs to consistent level (always engaged). A decrease in the number of beginning learners was revealed during the second quarter. Kindergartens' cognitive engagement is increased when they participate in experiential, hands-on learning activities. Children's cognitive growth is boosted by manipulating items, performing experiments, and working on real-world projects because they are actively creating new knowledge and making connections.

A study by Agbayani and Fajardo (2018) investigated the impact of teacher classroom management styles on the language development of kindergarten learners in the Philippines. The study found that teachers who used a positive and supportive classroom management style had a significant positive impact on the language development of kindergarten learners.

Furthermore, Rodriguez and Garcia (2018) observed that kindergarten learners exposed to an authoritative classroom management style exhibited more significant gains in literacy skills, including reading readiness, phonological awareness, and vocabulary development than learners in classrooms with authoritarian or permissive styles.

Table 11

Kindergarten Learners' Level of Cognitive Engagement-Numeracy

Quarter (SY 2023-2024)	Number of Learners	Numeracy					
		(C) Consistent		(D) Developing		(B) Beginning	
1st	5494	819	14.90 %	2766	50.35 %	1909	34.75 %
2nd	5440	1632	30 %	2650	48.71 %	1158	21.29 %

Legend:

C-Consistent (*The learner always demonstrates the competency.*)

D-Developing (*The learner sometimes demonstrates the competency.*)

B-Beginning (*The learner rarely demonstrates the competency.*)

Table 11 shows the result of kindergarten learners' level of cognitive engagement in numeracy. During the first quarter, majority of the learners, or **50.35 %** (2766 learners), belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), while **34.75 %** (1909 learners), belongs to the beginning level (rarely engaged), meanwhile the remaining **14.90 %** (819 learners), belongs to the consistent level (always engaged). As shown, half of the percentage of kindergarten learners falls under the developing level during the first quarter. A good start in the cognitive development of learners in numeracy. When kindergarten learners actively participate in their learning, such as through questioning, problem-solving, and critical thinking, they tend to exhibit higher levels of cognitive engagement. Deeper learning, knowledge retention, and cognitive growth are all facilitated by active participation. Moreover, cognitive engagement can be improved by giving children personalized education and learning experiences that match to their needs and interests. Active cognitive engagement is encouraged by recognizing and fostering each child's distinct cognitive abilities and posing suitable tasks. Meanwhile, during the second quarter majority of the learners or **48.71 %** (2650 learners), belongs to developing level (sometimes engaged), while **30 %** (1632 learners), belongs to consistent level (always engaged), meanwhile the remaining **21.29 %** (1158 learners), belongs to the beginning level (rarely engaged). An increase of the number of consistent learners was shown during the second quarter. Children's cognitive engagement is boosted by kindergarten tasks and activities relevant to and meaningful to them in real life. Enhancing intrinsic motivation and cognitive engagement is achieved through connecting learning to real-world, realistic circumstances and children's lives. Kindergarten play-based learning strategies promote cognitive engagement. As they participate in imaginative and symbolic play scenarios, children can actively explore, experiment, and build their problem-solving abilities through play.

Lee and Park (2021) indicated that kindergarten learners taught by authoritative teachers showed higher levels of mathematics achievement compared to learners in classrooms with authoritarian or permissive management styles. The study emphasized the importance of supportive and organized classroom environments for fostering mathematical skills development in young learners.

Part III. Significant Relationship between Classroom Management Styles Practiced by Kindergarten Teachers and the Level of Engagement of Kindergarten Learners

Table 12

Relationship between Kindergarten Teachers' Classroom Management Style and Learners' Level of Engagement for the First Quarter

Kindergarten Teachers' Classroom Management Style	Learners' Level of Engagement for the First Quarter	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Conclusion
Interventionist	Behavioral Engagement	0.083	Weak Positive	0.370	Not Significantly Correlated
	Emotional Engagement	0.049	Weak Positive	0.593	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Literacy	0.005	Weak Positive	0.958	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Numeracy	-0.098	Weak Negative	0.286	Not Significantly Correlated
Interactionist	Behavioral Engagement	0.145	Weak Positive	0.114	Not Significantly Correlated
	Emotional Engagement	0.064	Weak Positive	0.491	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Literacy	0.033	Weak Positive	0.724	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Numeracy	-0.106	Weak Negative	0.250	Not Significantly Correlated
Non-Interactionist	Behavioral Engagement	0.098	Weak Positive	0.287	Not Significantly Correlated
	Emotional Engagement	0.163	Weak Positive	0.074	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Literacy	0.076	Weak Positive	0.409	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Numeracy	-0.040	Weak Negative	0.663	Not Significantly Correlated

*Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 12 shows the correlation between kindergarten teachers' classroom management styles and the level of engagement demonstrated by kindergarten learners during the first quarter of instruction. Effective classroom management is essential for creating a conducive learning environment, while learner engagement indicates the effectiveness of teaching practices. Understanding the relationship between these variables sheds light on the dynamics of classroom interaction and instructional efficacy in kindergarten settings. As shown, the results revealed that there were weak and non-significant correlations between kindergarten teachers' classroom management styles and learners' levels of engagement across various dimensions during the first quarter. Regardless of whether teachers adapt an interventionist, interactionist, or non-interactionist classroom management style, correlations with behavioral engagement, emotional engagement, cognitive engagement in literacy, and cognitive engagement in numeracy are consistently weak and statistically insignificant. These results suggested that variations in classroom management styles do not significantly influence the level of engagement observed

among learners during the initial quarter of instruction. Generally, kindergarten is the start of formal schooling and during early stages of instruction, learners are adjusting to a new environment that differs from their previous experiences. While many learners attend preschool or other “school-like” setting prior to kindergarten, research indicates that only about 60% of learners experience a center-based care setting as their primary care arrangement in the year before kindergarten (Rathbun, Zhang, & Snyder, 2016). For the other 40% of learners, transitioning to the kindergarten context may be challenging. Moreover, even learners who attend center-based settings prior to kindergarten experience dramatic shifts as they enter kindergarten, in both environmental experiences and expectations. Additionally, learners are also held to different expectations in the kindergarten setting. These include academic expectations, which are demonstrated by the greater emphasis on skill development and the amount of time spent in learning-focused activities, and behavioral expectations, which include staying on task and following stricter routines.

Lack of significant correlations between classroom management styles and learner engagement could also mean an indication that other factors, such as instructional practices, individual learner characteristics, and classroom dynamics, play a more influential role in shaping engagement levels during the early stages of instruction. As such, educators may need to focus on implementing a diverse range of instructional strategies and differentiation techniques to foster engagement among a heterogeneous group of learners. Similarly, researchers should consider exploring additional variables and factors contributing to learner engagement in kindergarten settings, including teacher-learner interactions, curriculum design, and socio-emotional factors. By gaining a deeper understanding of the multifaceted nature of learner engagement, educators and researchers can collaborate to refine teaching practices and optimize learning experiences for young children in kindergarten classrooms.

Table 13

Kindergarten Teachers' Classroom Management Style	Learners' Level of Engagement for the Second Quarter	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Conclusion
Interventionist	Behavioral Engagement	-0.004	Weak Negative	0.963	Not Significantly Correlated
	Emotional Engagement	0.055	Weak Positive	0.551	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Literacy	0.033	Weak Positive	0.722	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Numeracy	-0.110	Weak Negative	0.231	Not Significantly Correlated
	Interactionist	Behavioral Engagement	0.162	Weak Positive	0.078
Interactionist	Emotional Engagement	0.189*	Weak Positive	0.038	Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Literacy	0.045	Weak Positive	0.624	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Numeracy				

	Cognitive Engagement-Numeracy	-0.019	Weak Negative	0.837	Not Significantly Correlated
Non-Interactionist	Behavioral Engagement	0.071	Weak Positive	0.442	Not Significantly Correlated
	Emotional Engagement	0.083	Weak Positive	0.370	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Literacy	0.044	Weak Positive	0.633	Not Significantly Correlated
	Cognitive Engagement-Numeracy	0.023	Weak Positive	0.799	Not Significantly Correlated

Relationship between Kindergarten Teachers' Classroom Management Style and Learners' Level of Engagement for the Second Quarter

*Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 13 presents the relationship between kindergarten teachers' classroom management styles and the level of engagement exhibited by kindergarten learners during the second quarter of instruction. About the correlation analysis done for the first quarter, effective classroom management is pivotal in creating an environment conducive to learning accounting for learners' journey in the classroom as continuous learners' engagement serves a crucial role for instructional effectiveness. As presented, the results revealed weak and mostly non-significant correlations between kindergarten teachers' classroom management styles and learners' levels of engagement across various dimensions during the second quarter. For teachers employing interventionist, interactionist, or non-interactionist classroom management style, correlations with behavioral engagement, emotional engagement, cognitive engagement in literacy, and cognitive engagement in numeracy generally demonstrate weak and statistically insignificant relationships. However, there was an exception, such as a weak positive correlation between the interactionist classroom management style and emotional engagement, which is statistically significant, suggesting a potential influence of this management style on learners' emotional engagement during the second quarter. Beyond academic outcomes, the kindergarten years play a vital role in shaping a child's personal development. Kindergarten provides opportunities for socialization, emotional growth, and the development of social skills such as cooperation, empathy, and communication. Hence, qualitative ratings are also preferred on summarizing learners' overall performance, as they are more suitable for the age and developmental stage of kindergarten learners, as opposed to numerical grades. Positive experiences during this time can enhance self-esteem, self-confidence, and overall social-emotional well-being, contributing to success in personal relationships and overall life satisfaction.

On the other hand, findings also suggested that the lack of significant correlations between classroom management styles and learner engagement during the second quarter may indicate that other factors, such as instructional strategies, learner characteristics, and classroom dynamics, may play a more influential role in shaping engagement levels as instruction progresses. This underscores the importance of employing a diverse range of instructional approaches and differentiation techniques to foster engagement among learners.

Additionally, the identification of a significant correlation between the interactionist classroom management style and emotional engagement suggests a potential avenue for further investigation into the specific mechanisms through which classroom management styles influence emotional engagement among learners. Researchers should explore additional variables and factors that may contribute to learner engagement over time, including teacher-learner interactions, curriculum adaptations, and socio-emotional dynamics, to gain a comprehensive understanding of instructional effectiveness in kindergarten classrooms.

Part IV. Proposed Lesson Plan Model Based on the Study's Findings

Findings revealed that public school kindergarten teachers in the Division of Lucena City highly integrate interactionist classroom management style to a Very Great Extent in teaching. It was also revealed on the study a significant correlation (weak positive correlation) between interactionist classroom management style and emotional engagement among kindergarten learners. Hence, a lesson plan model utilizing interactionist classroom management style highlighting emotional development among kindergarten learners was proposed by the researcher. The proposed lesson plan model includes the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) for the first quarter in the kindergarten level. The proposed lesson plan is a modified model of lesson plan that is currently used by kindergarten teachers in the division. Its key feature is integrating interactionist style on emotional development of learners. However, it also covers behavioral development, cognitive development in literacy and numeracy among kindergarten learners. It follows the blocks of times in kindergarten and incorporates “*I do, we do, you do*” approach in work periods which promotes interactions between the teacher and the learners.

DISCUSSION

The significant findings of the study are summarized below:

1. Extent of a Particular Classroom Management Style Practiced by Kindergarten Teachers

1.1. Interventionist classroom management style is practiced to a Great Extent by kindergarten teachers.

1.2. Interactionist classroom management style is practiced to a Very Great Extent by kindergarten teachers.

1.3. Non-interventionist classroom management style is practiced to a Moderately Extent by kindergarten teachers.

2. Level of Engagement of Kindergarten Learners

2.1. On the level of behavioral engagement, during the first quarter majority of the learners belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), while during the second quarter majority of the learners belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged).

2.2. On the level of emotional engagement, during the first quarter majority of the learners belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), whereas, during the second quarter majority of the learners belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged).

2.3 On the level of cognitive engagement:

2.3.1. across literacy domain, during the first quarter majority of the learners belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), whereas, during the second quarter majority of the learners belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged).

2.3.2. across numeracy domain, during the first quarter majority of the learners belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged), while during the second quarter majority of the learners belongs to the developing level (sometimes engaged).

3. Significant Relationship between Classroom Management Styles Practiced by Kindergarten Teachers and the Level of Engagement of Kindergarten Learners

3.1. The results revealed weak and non-significant correlations between kindergarten teachers' classroom management styles and learners' levels of engagement across various dimensions during the first quarter.

3.2. The results revealed weak and mostly non-significant correlations between kindergarten teachers' classroom management styles and learners' levels of engagement across various dimensions during the second quarter. However, there was a weak positive correlation between interactionist classroom management style and emotional engagement, which was statistically significant.

4. A lesson plan model utilizing interactionist classroom management style highlighting emotional development among kindergarten learners was proposed by the researcher.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Interactionist style was practiced to a Very Great Extent, by public school kindergarten teachers in the Division of Lucena City, followed by interventionist style to a Great Extent, and non-interventionist style to a Moderately Extent.

2. Based on the result, learners' level of engagement across behavioral, emotional, and cognitive (literacy and numeracy) dimensions during first and second quarters (initial and transitional stages) were on the developing level (sometimes engaged).

3. The result revealed that during the first quarter, classroom management styles and learners' engagement were not significantly correlated. Meanwhile, during the second quarter, there is a significant correlation (weak positive correlation) between interactionist classroom management style and learners' emotional engagement. Thus, the study rejects the research hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between teachers' classroom management style and learners' level of engagement.

4. A lesson plan model utilizing interactionist classroom management style highlighting emotional development among kindergarten learners was proposed by the researcher.

Recommendations

Given the preceding conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. Since the result showed that interactionist style was highly practiced classroom management style among public school kindergarten teachers in the Division of Lucena City, other teachers may also integrate an interactionist management style in their classroom setting that would foster engagement among learners.

2. Due to the findings that kindergarten learners' level of engagement during first and second quarters were on the developing level, teacher may use this study as reference for further development of their classroom management styles that would enhance result in the quarterly assessment of kindergarten learners.

4. Since the findings revealed that there is a significant correlation between interactionist classroom management style and learners' emotional engagement, teachers may adapt the proposed lesson plan model utilizing interactionist classroom management style that would enhance emotional engagement among kindergarten learners.

4. Since the result of the study only encompasses level of engagement of learners in the kindergarten level, future researchers may also look into other developmental stages. This study may also serve as their reference into further studying classroom management styles and factors affecting learners' engagement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured that informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondent's well-being as safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The researcher owes deepest gratitude to those who made this thesis a reality.

To Marinduque State College Graduate Studies Faculty and Staff, to Quezonian Educational College, Inc. Faculty and Staff, to Public School Kindergarten Teachers in the Division of Lucena City, to Elvira Razon Aranilla Elementary School Faculty and Staff, to her family and friends, to her boyfriend, Jun Marc G. Madriaga.

Above all else, to Almighty God.

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